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INVESTOR BEHAVIOR ON LIFE INSURANCE-WITH REFERENCE TO GRANITE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Investor Behavior is a crucial factor, which must be known to the marketing management. Investors have to play major role in protecting themselves from the cuts of businessmen. Most of the people are earning their income through granite factories and working various levels of positions. A buyers decision is also influenced by personal outwards characteristics, notably the buyers age and life cycle, stage ,economic circumstances, life styles and personality and self –concept. You receive financial compensation when an insured event occurs. Consider auto insurance, for example.

Key words: life policies , investments, granite workers, policy types.

INTRODUCTION:

Granite and marble are two main natural stones widely used in the stone industry. These stones are used in constructions as well as in monumental sculpture. Commercially, these stones are mined for use as architectural stones for flooring, cladding, curbing, counter tops and much more to be used at home.

Most of the people are earning their income through granite factories and working various levels of positions especially in Gundla Palli growth center most of the people are came from other states like Rajasthan, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh etc. these people are came from a long distance they did not know about the investment criteria's .

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Investor Behavior is a crucial factor, which must be known to the marketing management. Investors have to play major role in protecting themselves from the cutes of businessmen. The term Investor Behavior on refers to Investor While purchase, using disposing of the products which will satisfy their needs.

The marketer's Risk is to understand how the stimuli are transferred into responders inside the Investor black box has two components.

- 1) The Buyers characteristics influence how he perceives and reach to the stimuli.
- 2) The Buyers decision process itself influences out come.

Major Factors influencing investor behavior are cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Culture means religion and region will also influence on buyer's behavior. Social means income occupation, Education, Wealth etc., places an important role in buying behavior. A buyers decision is also influenced by personal out wards characteristics, notably the buyers age and life cycle, stage ,economic circumstances, life styles and personality and self –concept .Finally the buying behavior also depends on the psychologically factors such as motivation perception, learning beliefs and attitudes.

Life insurance is a contract that pledges payment of an amount to the person assured (or his nominee) on the happening of the event insured against. The contract is valid for payment of the insured amount during:

- The date of maturity,
- Specified dates at periodic intervals,
- Unfortunate death, if it occurs earlier.

Life insurance is civilization's partial solution to the problems caused by death. Life insurance, in short, is concerned with two hazards that stand across the life-path of every person:

An investors passes through five stages before buying a product, i.e., he goes through a decision process consisting of:

- 1) Problem recognition
- 2) Information search
- 3) Evolution of alternative
- 4) Purchase decision and
- 5) Post purchase behavior

Life Insurance:

Most people have a basic understanding of insurance. You receive financial compensation when an insured event occurs. Consider auto insurance, for example. If your car is in an accident or stolen, your insurance company provides compensation according to the terms outlined in your insurance policy. On the surface, life insurance is pretty straightforward. When the insured person dies, the policy pays a prearranged amount to the designated beneficiary.

Purchase Life Insurance:

The main purpose of any life insurance policy is to protect your family and loved ones against the risk of financial uncertainty. Life insurance can provide for the welfare of your family in face of your death. If you have a spouse, three kids, a mortgage, car payments, and credit card bills, what would happen to them if you were suddenly to die?

Types of life insurance:

There are two basic forms of life insurance — term life and permanent life, the latter of which comes in several flavors. Here’s a quick breakdown of the basic policy types:

Term Life:

It is the simplest and (typically) cheapest form of life insurance. Term life is designed to provide coverage for a fixed period of time, such as 5, 10, or 20 years.

Whole Life:

Its policies, for example, are designed to provide you and your loved one with coverage until your death. Unlike term life, there are no fixed periods for whole life coverage. Whole life is sometimes referred to as “cash value” insurance because it builds cash value over your lifetime.

Universal Life:

It is a popular option that acts like whole life. It is a renewable policy the investment component, premiums, and death benefits can be renewed and changed based upon the policy owner’s needs.

Research problem: Investor behavior of life insurance products

METHODOLOGY:

Methodology concerning a research problem or study provide answers to various questions like; why a research study has been undertaken, how the research problem has been defined, what data have been collected and what particular method has been adopted to collect the data, what technique has been used for analyzing the data and a host of similar other questions.

Primary Sources of Data:

The primary data was collected with the help of a well designed questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed in such a way so as to elicit maximum amount of information from the respondents. Few questions are related to investor’s degrees of condition for various dimensions of investment. Some related to their preferences for life insurance products .

Sampling Size:

From this universe a sample of 100 was selected from GundlaPalli growth center, Prakasam district.

Sampling Method:

Convenience Sampling Method

Data analysis:

Do you know life insurance policies:

option	No of Respondents	%of Respondents
Yes	30	30
No	70	70
Total	100	100

Above table shows majority of respondents did not know about the life policies ,only few people know the life policies.

What is your opinion on bonus of the policy :

option	No of Respondents	%of Respondents
Satisfied	60	60
Dissatisfied	25	25
Neutral	15	15
Total	100	100

Majority of the people are satisfied with bonuses of the exiting policies, some are expressing their dissatisfaction about bonus.

What is your opinion on Introduction of New policies

option	No of Respondents	%of Respondents
Good	70	70
Not bad	30	30
Total	100	100

The above table shows introduction of new policies are good for they are investing their investments in new policies

What extent are you preserve money.

Option	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents(%)
Bank Savings	41	41
Purchasing furniture	24	24
Investing on land	35	35
Total	100	100

In the above table shows they are investing their investments majorly banking savings and investing on lands.

Conclusion:

In my analysis Most of the people working in granite industry in this area they did not know about the life policies. these people mainly investing their investments in banks they are not having much more investment techniques why because most of them are illiterates. By introducing new policies it can attract more customers to take policies from it. Provide better coverage on every insurance policy. Money returned policies can attracted the customer .Short term policies can be choose by most number of policy holders, so try to introduce more policies on that. Insurances companies tries to concentrate on rural areas especially in growth centers. here different people are came from different places that's why they are fear about their investment ,companies ,agents taking initiation to aware the people need for the life policies and guiding them to invest in right way.

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